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Tissue ELISA and serum amperometric magnetoimmunosensor of ECD-HER2 validity in the stratification of breast cancer subtypes among Egyptian female patients

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Abstract

Background: HER2 status is an important diagnostic and prognostic marker in breast cancers (BCs). Yet the applicability of HER2 extracellular domain (ECD) amperometric magnetoimmunosensor on patients' samples is not tested.

Methods: Blood and tissues collected from 72 females (20 controls, five recurrent breast tumours, and 47 BCs). Tissue (tHER2) and serum HER2 (sHER2) detected by ELISA and the amperometric magnetoimmunosensor (AM) and their levels correlated to the clinicopathological parameters, and serum CA15-3 (sCA15-3).

Results: tHER2 (ELISA) and sCA15-3 significantly differed among the studied groups. tHER2 (ELISA) decreased significantly with higher BMI in HER2²⁺ group. tHER2 and sHER2 (AM) correlated significantly in HER2³⁺ group. tHER2 (ELISA) differed significantly among BCs molecular subtypes. Both tHER2 and sHER2 (ELISA) correlated significantly in HER2 molecular subgroup. sHER2 (AM) showed high significant sensitivity and specificity in differentiating TN from luminal A at > 9.26 ng/ml and HER2 at 9.6 ng/ml. However, at > 1.67 ng/ml, tHER2 (ELISA) stratified significantly between BCs molecular and HER2 subgroups.

Conclusions: In conclusion, tissue ELISA and serum AM provided useful quantitative measurements for HER2 in various BC subtypes (at cut off values lower than that approved by FDA) and would complement the current IHC and ISHs techniques.

Keywords

Aamperometric immunosensor; Body Mass Index; Breast cancer subtypes; Chemiluminescence immunoassay; ELISA, HER2 ECD

Introduction

Accurate assessment of Human epidermal growth factor receptor-2 (HER2) status is crucial for both tailored targeted therapeutic and follow up strategies of breast cancers (BCs) [1]. HER2, proto-oncogene, encodes a tyrosine kinase (TK) growth factor receptor protein that is expressed by several normal tissues and has a role in normal cell function, regulation of cell growth, proliferation, differentiation, development, and survival [2]. HER2 receptor has three main domains; an extracellular domain (ECD), an intermembrane domain, and a TK intracellular domain [3]. HER2 ECD (p105; from 95 to 105 KDa) is cleaved by metalloproteases- as one of the activation mechanisms- and released into the blood [4]. It is detected in patients with primary and metastatic breast cancer. It is suggested to be a surrogate tumour marker that correlates with overexpression of tissue HER2 (tHER2) and worse prognosis in metastatic BC [5].

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) developed and approved by Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to quantify ECD of HER2 in blood and tissue lysates providing low detection limits [3, 6]. This is important as the HER2 targeted therapy of advanced BC relies on the primary tumour HER2 status and some studies reported HER2 receptor conversion after neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) or during metastasis progression [7]. This conversion will affect the therapeutic decision and treatment response and thus necessitate re-evaluation in post-NAC specimens and metastatic lesions.

Biosensors, as analytical devices containing a bio-recognition layer on the surface of a transducer, can offer the straightforward advantage of being able to convert a biological event into an electronic signal and to distinguish a specific biomarker in complex matrices [8]. Immunosensors have been well established as valid alternatives to classical analyses of cancer biomarkers by offering the advantages of being easy to use, rapid, inexpensive, and capable of

multianalyte testing [9]. Several types of biosensors developed and used successfully to quantify HER2 with low detection limits [10-14].

Cancer antigen 15-3 (CA 15-3) is a frequently used marker in BC which detects the soluble moiety of the transmembrane mucin-1 (MUC1) protein- a coreceptor of HER2 and a key player in aberrant O-glycosylation and distant metastasis [15-17]. According to various guidelines, CA15-3 may be used in monitoring and follow up [18]. Nowadays, the electrochemiluminescence (ECL) detection method of CA 15-3 became the most used method because of its high sensitivity and low detection limit [18].

The current study was designed to compare the efficiency, specificity, and the sensitivity of the conventional tHER2 immunohistochemistry (IHC) with both ELISA and an amperometric magnetoimmunosensor assay in detecting both tHER2 and serum (sHER2); respectively. The correlation between clinicopathological parameters and CA 15-3 level were also investigated.

Results

The clinicopathological data presented in supplementary 1. The results showed a shift towards the postmenopausal status, a broader range of age, lower frequency of IDC with the appearance of aggressive mixed types, less tumour size ($> 4 = 28.8$), less cases with LNM (53.8 %), slight decrease in grades II & III (89.4%), and minor increase in the frequency of stage III & IV (71.2). The results also inferred a high impact of overweight or obesity (of variable classes) in BC development and progression in Egyptian female patients. Most of BC tumours were left sided that had higher frequency in HER2 (as detected by IHC) negative tumours than positive ones (78.6 versus 57.6%).

Although age significantly differed among the studied groups [$p = 0.007$ in Her-2 subtypes & $p = 0.037$ in molecular subtypes), age variation did not show any significant relation to the tHER2 status ($p = 0.170$) or BC molecular subtypes ($p = 0.294$); as detected by ELISA. Therefore, the observed significant difference of tHER2 ($p = 0.045$) among HER2 and BC molecular subtypes ($p = 0.017$) was age independent.

A significant direct correlation observed between tHER2 and sHER2 levels as detected by ELISA in HER2 enriched subgroup only ($r = 0.857$, $p = 0.014$) and in HER2³⁺ group as detected by AM ($r = 0.9$, $p = 0.037$) (Table 1). tHER2 (ELISA) significantly decreased ($p = 0.02$) with

higher Body Mass Index (BMI) in equivocal HER2 (2+) BC subgroup. This group was characterized by being mainly postmenopausal (71.4%), hormonal positive (ER⁺ & PR⁺: 76.02%), obese (BMI ≥ 30: 52.4%), and having luminal B (76.2%) BC molecular subtypes.

The current results showed for the first time the utility of sHER2 and tHER2 (as detected by Am and ELISA; respectively) in the differentiation of BC molecular subtypes at cut of values > 1.76 (for ELISA; specificity: 85.71-87.5%; sensitivity: 60-100%), > 9.26, and > 9.6 ng/ml (for AM; specificity: 83-100%; sensitivity: 100%) (Figure 1) in both primary and metastatic BC molecular subtypes.

sCA15-3 ($p = 0.048$) significantly differed among the studied groups with no relevance to the level of HER2. No significant correlation between long term disease-free survival and levels of ER, PR, and HER2, was detected in our study. Most of our cases had NPI ranging from excellent to moderate scores even after inclusion of HER2 score in NPI of HER2 positive BC cases (Table 2).

Supplementary 1. The demographic and clinicopathological parameters of the studied groups.

<i>Parameters</i>	Control (N = 20)	Recurrent Breast Tumours (N = 5)	Breast Cancer (N = 47)			
			HER2 status (as detected by IHC) (Wolff <i>et al.</i>, 2018)			
			Negative		Equivocal	Positive
			HER2 (0) (N = 6)	HER2 (1+) (N = 8)	HER2 (2+) (N = 21)	HER2 (3+) (N = 12)
N (%)						
<i>Age (Years)</i>						
<i>Mean ± SD</i>	48.75 ± 8.67	37.6 ± 15.1	52 ± 13	59 ± 11	55.90 ± 11.71	48.75 ± 10.75
<i>Other diseases</i>						
<i>Prediabetic</i>	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Diabetes</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
<i>Diastolic dysfunction</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	1 (8.3)
<i>Hypertension</i>	2 (10)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	4 (19)	1 (8.3)
<i>Hypertension + diabetes</i>	4 (20)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (25)	1 (4.8)	2 (16.7)
<i>Hypertension + Anaemia</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Hypertension + CVD</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>Hypertension + Hypercholesteremia</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>Arthritis</i>	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

<i>Axillary LN diseases</i>	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Liver diseases</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>None</i>	11 (55)	3 (60)	2 (33.3)	5 (62.5)	12 (57)	7 (58.3)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Menopausal status</i>						
<i>Pre</i>	9 (45)	3 (60)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	5 (23.8)	6 (50)
<i>Post</i>	10 (50)	0 (0)	4 (66.66)	7 (87.5)	15 (71.4)	3 (25)
<i>Irregular</i>	1 (5)	2 (40)	1 (16.66)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	3 (25)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (16.66)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>BI-RADS</i>						
<i>0</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>1</i>	14 (70)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>2</i>	6 (30)	1 (20)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>3</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	1 (8.3)
<i>4</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	2 (25)	7 (33.3)	7 (58.3)
<i>5</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	4 (50)	10 (47.6)	3 (25)
<i>6</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	1 (16.7)	2 (25)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	2 (40)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Tumour side</i>						
<i>Left</i>	-	2 (40)	5 (83.3)	6 (75)	13 (61.9)	6 (50)
<i>Right</i>	-	2 (40)	1 (16.7)	1 (12.5)	8 (38.1)	6 (50)
<i>Bilateral</i>	-	1 (20)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Tumor histological type</i>						
<i>Benign tumors</i>						

<i>Desmoid Tumour</i>	-	1 (20)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>(fibromatosis)</i>	-	2 (40)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Ductal epithelial hyperplasia</i>	-	2 (40)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Lobular granulomatous mastitis</i>						
<u>Carcinoma</u>						
<i>In situ carcinoma</i>	-	0 (0)	0(0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
<i>Ductal</i>						
<i>Invasive carcinoma (NOS)</i>	-	0 (0)	4 (66.7)	7 (87.5)	15 (71.4)	10 (83.3)
<i>Ductal</i>	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	0 (0)
<i>Mixed ductal & lobular</i>						
<i>Invasive carcinoma (special types)</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>Mucinous</i>						
<i>Others</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
<i>Paget & IDC with highly grad intraductal component</i>						
<i>(Comedo)</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>IDC & Focal mucoid lobular & Paget's</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>Paget's disease & intraductal</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)

<i>components</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Multifocal IDC 10% in situ components (comedo & cribriform)</i>	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Bifocal Invasive Lobular Carcinoma & in situ lobular components</i>						
<i>Tumour size (cm)</i>						
< 2	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	3 (14.3)	1 (8.3)
2-4	-	1 (20)	2 (33.3)	7 (87.5)	15 (71.4)	8 (66.7)
> 4	-	2 (40)	3 (50)	0 (0)	3 (14.3)	3 (25)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	2 (40)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Tumour Grade</i>						
<i>II</i>	-	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	6 (75)	12 (57.1)	9 (75)
<i>III</i>	-	0 (0)	3 (50)	2 (25)	5 (23.8)	3 (25)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	4 (19)	0 (0)
<i>Tumour stage</i>						
<i>DIS</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>I</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>IIA</i>	-	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	3 (14.3)	3 (25)
<i>IIIA</i>	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	2 (25)	5 (23.8)	4 (33.3)
<i>IB</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	0 (0)
<i>IIB</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	2 (9.5)	4 (33.3)

IIIB	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	1 (12.5)	2 (9.5)	0 (0)
IV	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (19)	1 (8.3)
Unknown	-	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
LNM						
<i>Negative</i>	-	4 (80)	3 (50)	2 (25)	9 (42.9)	5 (41.7)
<i>Positive</i>	-	1 (20)	3 (50)	6 (75)	12 (57.1)	6 (50)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
Number of the involved LN						
<i>0</i>	-	4 (80)	3 (50)	2 (25)	9 (42.9)	5 (41.7)
<i>1 (1-3)</i>	-	1 (20)	1 (16.7)	1 (12.5)	5 (23.8)	2 (16.7)
<i>2 (4-9)</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (37.5)	2 (9.5)	2 (16.7)
<i>3 (>10)</i>	-	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	5 (23.8)	2 (16.7)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
Vascular invasion						
Positive	-	0 (0)	6 (100)	7 (87.5)	18 (85.7)	12 (100)
Negative	-	5 (100)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	3 (14.3)	0 (0)
ER						
<i>0</i>	-	-	4 (66.7)	1 (12.5)	5 (23.8)	4 (33.3)
<i>1+</i>	-	-	0 (0)	4 (50)	1 (4.8)	3 (25)
<i>2+</i>	-	-	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	6 (28.6)	3 (25)
<i>3+</i>	-	-	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	9 (42.9)	2 (16.7)
PR						
<i>0</i>	-	-	4 (66.7)	2 (25)	5 (23.8)	4 (33.3)
<i>1+</i>	-	-	0 (0)	2 (25)	4 (19)	4 (33.3)

2+	-	-	0 (0)	2 (25)	3 (14.3)	1 (8.3)
3+	-	-	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	9 (42.9)	3 (25)
sHER2 (ng/ml)						
ELISA (M ± SD)						
Serum	3.61 ± 3.2	2.85 ± 0.37	5.4 ± 5.6	3.18 ± 0.92	3.99 ± 3.64	6.58 ± 6.16
Tissue	-	-	5.23 ± 6.38	1.74 ± 1.61	4.79 ± 4.13	6.80 ± 6.40
MBs (M ± SD)						
Serum	-	5.72 ± 0.64	11.16 ± 3.56	7.99 ± 6.76	9.90 ± 6.41	9.15 ± 11.19
Tissue	-	-	28.18 ± 58.7	17.21 ± 45.97	87.21 ± 166.95	125.9 ± 122.34
sCA15-3 (U/ml)						
M ± SD	17.89 ± 8.44	12.18 ± 5.03	21.31 ± 10.51	28.97 ± 9.54	19.55 ± 12.3	16.26 ± 7.46
> 34.5 (cut off value)	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (25)	2 (9.5)	0 (0)
≤ 34.5	19 (95)	5 (100)	6 (100)	6 (75)	19 (90.5)	12 (100)
BMI (Kg/m²)						
< 18.5 (underweight)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
18.5-24.99 (healthy)	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
25-29.99 (overweight)	5 (25)	3 (60)	1 (16.7)	2 (25)	7 (33.3)	4 (33.3)
≥ 30 (obese)	14 (70)	1 (20)	3 (50)	5 (62.5)	11 (52.4)	7 (58.3)
Class I (30-34.99)	6 (30)	1 (20)	3 (50)	3 (37.5)	4 (19)	4 (33.3)
Class II (35-39.99)	5 (25)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (25)	5 (23.8)	1 (8.3)
Class III ≥ 40	3 (15)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	2 (16.6)
Unknown	0 (0)	1 (20)	2 (33.3)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
Outcomes						
Alive	-	4 (80)	4 (66.7)	8 (100)	19 (90.5)	12 (100)

<i>Died</i>	-	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	0 (0)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	1 (20)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Free</i>	-	3 (60)	4 (66.7)	4 (50)	12 (57.1)	9 (75)
<i>Local recurrence</i>	-	1 (20)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	2 (16.7)
<i>Metastasis</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (23.8)	0 (0)
<i>Local recurrence plus metastasis</i>	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	1 (20)	2 (33.3)	4 (50)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>NPI</i>						
<i>Excellent (2.02-2.4)</i>	-	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (14.3)	2 (16.7)
<i>Good (2.4-3.4)</i>	-	-	1 (16.7)	1 (12.5)	3 (14.3)	3 (25)
<i>Moderate 1 (3.41-4.4)</i>	-	-	3 (50)	1 (12.5)	3 (14.3)	2 (16.7)
<i>Moderate 2 (4.41-5.4)</i>	-	-	0 (0)	2 (25)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>Poor (5.41-6.4)</i>	-	-	1 (16.7)	3 (37.5)	4 (19)	1 (8.3)
<i>Very poor (6.41-6.8)</i>	-	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>Unknown</i>	-	-	1 (16.7)	1 (12.5)	4 (19)	2 (16.7)
<i>Socioeconomic status</i>						
<i>High</i>	3 (15)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Middle</i>	7 (35)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	4 (33.3)
<i>Low</i>	10 (50)	4 (80)	2 (33.3)	8 (100)	19 (94.5)	8 (66.7)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>Breast feeding</i>						

<i>Yes</i>	16 (80)	2# (40)	3 (50)	3 (37.5)	17## (81)	10 (83.3)
<i>No</i>	4 (20)	2 (40)	0 (0)	5 (62.5)	4 (19)	2 (16.7)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Number of pregnancies lasting ≥ 6 months						
<i>0</i>	1 (5)	1 (20)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	1 (4.8)	2 (16.7)
<i>1</i>	1 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	0 (0)	1 (8.3)
<i>2</i>	7 (35)	1 (20)	0 (0)	4 (50)	6 (28.6)	2 (16.7)
<i>3</i>	3 (15)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>≥ 4</i>	8 (40)	2 (40)	2 (33.3)	2 (25)	12 (57.1)	6 (50)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Smoking						
<i>Nonsmokers</i>	9 (45)	2 (40)	2 (33.3)	4 (50)	7 (33.3)	6 (50)
<i>Passive smokers</i>	11 (55)	2 (40)	1 (16.7)	4 (50)	13 (62)	6 (50)
<i>Active smokers</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8)	0 (0)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Family history						
<i>Yes</i>	4 (20)	2 (40)	1 (16.7)	2 (25)	6 (28.6)	2 (16.7)
<i>No</i>	16 (80)	2 (40)	2 (33.3)	6 (75)	15 (71.4)	10 (83.3)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Oral contraceptives						
<i>Yes</i>	5 (25)	1 (20)	0 (0)	2 (25)	4 (19)	4 (33.3)
<i>No</i>	15 (75)	3 (60)	3 (50)	6 (75)	17 (81)	8 (66.7)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Hormone replacement

therapy

<i>Yes</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (12.5)	2 (9.5)	1 (8.3)
<i>No</i>	20 (100)	4 (80)	3 (50)	7 (87.5)	19 (90.5)	11 (91.7)
<i>Unknown</i>	0 (0)	1 (20)	3 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

LN: lymph node; CVD: cardiovascular diseases; NOS: no special type.

TABLE 1. CORRELATION BETWEEN SHER2 AND THER2 USING ELISA AND AM ASSAYS IN THE DIFFERENT STUDIED GROUPS.

	Molecular subtypes							
	TN		LUM A		LUM B		Her-2	
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p
ELISA (SHER2 VS. THER2)	0.800	0.104	-	0.233	0.309	0.151	0.857	0.014*
			0.476					
AM (SHER2 VS. THER2)	0.500	0.391	0.609	0.109	0.224	0.533	1.000	-
ELISA (THER2 VS. AGE)	-	0.873	0.595	0.120	0.183	0.403	-	0.294
	0.100						0.464	
ELISA (THER2 VS. CA 15-3)	-	0.391	-	0.420	0.032	0.886	0.286	0.535
	0.500		0.333					
	HER2 status (as detected by IHC)							
	Negative		Her-2 (2+)		Her-2 (3+)			
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p		
ELISA (SHER2 VS. THER2)	0.330	0.271	0.319	0.183	0.091	0.790		
AM (SHER2 VS. THER2)	0.245	0.420	0.433	0.244	0.900	0.037*		
ELISA (THER2 VS. AGE)	-	0.865	-0.024	0.923	0.445	0.170		
	0.052							
ELISA (THER2 VS. CA 15-3)	-	0.566	0.118	0.632	0.218	0.519		
	0.176							

r_s : Spearman coefficient; *: Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

TABLE 2. PROGNOSIS OF HER-2 (2⁺) EQUIVOCAL AND HER-2 (3⁺) GROUPS ACCORDING TO NPI AND THE REVISED NPI.

PARAMETERS	Her-2 (2 ⁺) (as detected by IHC)						Her-2 (3 ⁺) (as detected by IHC)					
	(N = 21)						(N = 12)					
	NPI	DFS	OS (%)	Revised	DFS%	OS%	NPI	DFS (%)	OS (%)	Revised	DFS%	OS%
	N (%)	(%)		NPI			N (%)			NPI		
PROGNOSIS	N (%)						N (%)					
EXCELLENT (2.02 - 2.4)	3 (14.3)	66.7	100	0 (0)	-	-	2 (16.7)	100	100	0 (0)	-	-
GOOD (2.4 - 3.4)	3 (14.3)	66.7	66.7	4 (19)	37	66.7	3 (25)	0	100	4 (33.3)	100	100
MODERATE 1 (3.41 - 4.4)	3 (14.3)	33.3	100	4 (19)	75	100	2 (16.7)	100	100	2 (16.7)	0	100
MODERATE 2 (4.41 - 5.4)	3 (14.3)	33.3	100	3 (14.3)	33.3	100	1 (8.3)	100	100	2 (16.7)	100	100
POOR (5.41 - 6.4)	3 (14.3)	33.3	66.7	3 (14.3)	33.3	66.7	1 (8.3)	100	100	0 (0)	-	-
VERY POOR (6.41 - 6.8)	2 (9.5)	100	100	3 (14.3)	66.7	100	1 (8.3)	0	100	2 (16.7)	50	100
UNKNOWN	4 (19)	75	100	4 (19)	75	100		2 (16.7)	50	100	2 (16.7)	100

Figure 1. ROC curves to diagnose BC subtypes. sHER2 by AM; **A)** AUC: 1, p : 0.003*, 95% C.I.: 1-1, cut off: >9.26, sensitivity: 100, specificity: 100, PPV: 100, NPV: 100. **B)** AUC: 0.867, p : 0.045*, 95% C.I.: 0.615-1.118, cut off: >9.6, sensitivity: 100, specificity: 83.33, PPV: 83.3, NPV: 100. tHER2 by ELISA; **C)** AUC: 0.850; p : 0.040*; 95% C.I.: 0.608-1.092, cut off: >1.67, sensitivity: 60, specificity: 87.5, PPV: 75, NPV: 77.8. **D)** AUC: 0.859, p : 0.003*, 95% C.I.: 0.698-1.019, cut off: >1.67, sensitivity: 82.61, specificity: 87.50, PPV: 95, NPV: 60. **E)** AUC: 0.893, p : 0.011*, 95% C.I.: 0.691-1.094, cut off: >1.67, sensitivity: 100, specificity: 87.5, PPV: 87.5, NPV: 100. **F)** AUC: 0.812, p : 0.016*, 95% C.I.: 0.600-1.024, cut off: >1.67, sensitivity: 84.21, specificity: 85.71, PPV: 94.1, NPV: 66.7. **G)** AUC: 0.909, p : 0.004*, 95% C.I.: 0.753-1.065, cut off: >1.67, sensitivity: 90.91, specificity: 85.71, PPV: 90.9, NPV: 85.7. AUC: Area Under a Curve; p value: Probability value; CI: Confidence intervals; NPV: Negative predictive value; PPV: Positive predictive value; #Cut off was chosen according to Youden index; *: Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Discussion

The current study is the first study performed on patients' samples using the HER2 AM and documented the utility of sHER2 and tHER2 (as detected by Am and ELISA; respectively) in the differentiation of BC molecular subtypes in both primary and metastatic BC at cut of values lower than the approved value (15 ng/ml) for the current assays. It showed that the relation between tissue and serum HER2 in certain BC subgroups depends on specific characteristics of those groups. Also, it shed the light on the current clinicopathological features of the BC among Egyptian females.

Studies based on National cancer institute (NCI, Cairo, Egypt) registries showed that the profile of BC in Egyptian BC patients is characterised by median age of 47.5 ± 11 years (26-80), premenopausal status (60.5%), large tumour size (mean = 4.5 cm), positive lymph node metastasis (LNM; 75%), positive oestrogen receptor (ER: 40.9%), positive progesterone receptor (PR: 31.4%), grade II (85.6%), stage III (56.8%), infiltrating ductal carcinoma (IDC) (83.4-84.5%), no prior family history of cancer (63%), and low socioeconomical status [19, 20]. The shift documented by the current and previous studies [21-23] (from medical research institute, Alexandria, Egypt) might indicate an increased awareness and early detection resulted from the screening programs that were established by Alexandria university and Medical research institute. A significant difference ($p = 0.0146$) in the presentation of BC also observed previously between Tanta and Cairo cases [24]. Therefore, each part of Egypt has its own distinguished impact on BC characteristics.

The results emphasised the role of high body weight and hormonal dependency of BC among Egyptian females. White adipose tissue (WAT) inflammation identified as a key driver for hormone-dependent BC in postmenopausal women [25, 26]. Hyperinsulinemia and renin-angiotensin system (RAS) also associate with obesity and higher risk factors of BC [27, 28]. However, diabetes and hypertension had a very low contribution among our BC cases.

Current data also showed a preferentiality towards left side BC among Egyptian females. Similarly, a study involved 5459 BCs from Gharbiah in Egypt showed higher left sided BCs

which tends to be lobular cancers and have worse survival [29]. However, in our data left side tumours were mainly IDC and of mixed lobular and IDC in a few cases. The preferentiality of left side in BC is speculated to be due to the activation of growth and transcription factors that were embryonically active during specification of the left-right asymmetry [30].

The absence of an association between the age variation among BC subtypes was detected in the current and our previous studies [21, 22]. In contrary to our results, significant age variation ($p = 0.05$) reported in a study conducted on 49 Egyptian females with IDC where higher expression of HER2 (as detected by IHC & RT-PCR) was detected in younger and older ages (100% in < 35 years and 91% in > 50 years; respectively) while ages from 35-50 years showed intermediate expression (67%) [31]. These conflicting data might implicate variability in the studied populations, the clinicopathological characteristics, the used assay, and/or the cut off values.

Although HER2 status is an important diagnostic and prognostic marker in BC, yet the validity of HER2 extracellular domain (ECD) as a surrogate maker is not approved due to controversial results. However, our current results showed significant direct correlation between tHER2 and sHER2 levels in some BC subgroups (HER2 enriched subgroup and in HER2³⁺ groups). Similarly, a study on 545 unselected Chinese primary BC without prior treatment, sHER2 ECD (measured by immunoassay) related to tHER2 [measured by IHC or fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (FISH)] [32]. However, 36.9% of patients with tHER-2 overexpression had <15 ng/ml of sHER2 reflecting low shedding activity. Cell culture models revealed that the HER2 shedding activity is alpha-secretase and disintegrin and metalloproteinase domain-containing protein10 (ADAM10) dependent and the progression-free survival (PFS) of BC patients with tHER-2 IHC³⁺ and sHER-2 ECD > 15 ng/ml was lower than those with serum HER-2 ECD <15 ng/ml [32]. Recently, Fabricio *et al.*, also reported high association and concordance between sHER2 and tHER2 levels rather than HER2 intracellular receptor domain (ICD) in HER2³⁺ subgroup (as detected by IHC) [5]. Krüger *et al.*, [33] attributed the absence of such correlation with other HER2 status to the “heterogeneity of ECD loss at the single-cell level, and in different areas of individual tumours”.

The reverse association between tHER2 and body mass index (BMI) in equivocal HER2 (2+) BC subgroup stems from the main characteristics of this subgroup; obese, postmenopausal status, hormonal positive status, and luminal B tumours). Studies documented a positive association between overweight or obesity and the risk of luminal BC molecular subtype amongst postmenopausal women with positive hormonal receptors status [34-36]. It was suggested that abdominal fat plays an important role in developing specific BC molecular subtypes and insulin resistance amongst postmenopausal women especially those with hormone receptor positive subtypes [37]. It is evident now that each subtype has a characteristic source of energy and metabolic profile [26, 36, 38]. Luminal subtypes upregulate de novo fatty acid synthesis and β -oxidation, TN depends on the exogenous fatty acids, and HER2 enriched subtype relies on the de novo fatty acid synthesis, storage, and oxidation [26, 36, 39]. Moreover, recent findings showed inter- and intra-variations in the lipidomes of the various molecular BC subtypes [39]. HER2 can also cross talk with oestrogen in the breast adipose tissue and acts as a key driver of breast cancer growth, development, stemness, and drug resistance [38-40].

Serum HER2 ECD varies according to the used assay, cut off values, presence of serum interfering factors, kinetics nature of serum HER2 ECD, ethnic population, BC progression, tumour stage, size and origin of the tumour [41]. In a study on 322 advanced breast cancer, serum HER2 ECD (detected by ELISA) differed significantly between BC molecular subtypes ($p < 0.001$), tHER2, number of metastatic sites, visceral metastasis, sCA15-3 and carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) [42]. A cut-off value of 7.4 ng/ml (sensitivity: 72.9%, specificity: 85.3%) was the best diagnostic cut-off value for early stage BC [43]. Recent meta-analysis for 40 studies revealed low sensitivity and a reasonable specificity, accuracy and area under the curve (AUC) of serum HER2 levels (detected by ELISA and/or CLIA; reference methods: IHC or IHC/FISH) “as a verification test for initial negative screening test results, especially in low income regions due to its cost-effectiveness and ease of implementation” [44]. This further support the value of our current findings of the utility of sHER2 and tHER2 using Am and ELISA (respectively) in the differentiation of BC molecular subtypes at low cut of values in both primary and metastatic BC molecular subtypes.

Despite the significant difference of CA15-3 among the studied groups, no relevance to the level of HER2 was detected in the current study. Similarly, despite a significant increase of

sCA15-3 in metastatic than preoperative group ($p = 0.002$) and in both preoperative and metastatic groups when compared with controls ($p = 0.016$; $p < 0.001$; respectively), our previous study [17] detected no significant relation between sCA15-3 and any of the tumour prognostic factors, age, or patients' outcome. On the other hand, Perrie *et al.*, [45] showed the validity of serum HER2, CA15.3, and CEA levels for predicting differential therapeutic response and “for monitoring HER2-targeted therapy in patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. The average decrease of the three biomarkers with a threshold of $> 10\%$ appeared to be the best parameter to distinguish patients who will develop a progressive disease from those whom will have other responses (complete, partial, or stable responses).

Although, Dong *et al.*, [46] reported a significant correlation between long term disease-free survival and levels of ER, PR, and HER2, this relation was absent in our study. This would be attributed to the fact that most of our cases had NPI ranging from excellent to moderate scores (even after inclusion of HER2 score in NPI of HER2 positive BC cases), lower number of ER negative and TNBC according to Al jarroudi *et al.*, [47] and Juneja *et al.*, [48].

In conclusion, tHER2 tissue (ELISA) and sHER2 (AM) provided useful quantitative measurements for HER2 in various BC subtypes. Both techniques would complement the current IHC and FISH techniques to derive a better understanding of the dynamic profile of HER2 in diagnosis and prognosis of BC. Future multicentre comparative and validation studies are mandatory.

Methods

Subjects (72) were randomly selected from patients referred to the Medical Research Institute (MRI), Alexandria University (AU), Egypt (from August 2017 to November 2018) and sample size was based on previously published work [17]. Blood (preoperative) and tissue (during elective surgery) samples were collected from subjects according to the ethical rules approved by the ethics committee of the medical research institute, Alexandria University, Egypt (IORG 0008812) (<https://mri.alexu.edu.eg/index.php/en/research-ethics/research-ethics-guidelines>). The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki (1964) and its subsequent amendments (https://mri.alexu.edu.eg/images/Declaration_of_Helsinki.pdf). After history taking, clinical

examinations, informed consent taking, routine laboratory, and radiological investigations, subjects were subdivided into the following groups:

1. Control group: Included 20 females with no evidence of any primary or secondary breast cancer as detected by mammography and breast ultrasound (US) (if required).
2. Recurrent breast tumours: included five females.
3. HER2 negative breast cancer group: [Zero (6) & 1⁺ (8)]: Included 14 females with breast carcinomas.
4. HER2 equivocal breast cancer group (2⁺): Included 21 females with breast carcinomas.
5. HER2 positive breast cancer group (3⁺): Included 12 females with breast carcinomas.

Patients were treated and followed up [17] for a period of three years. Pathological investigations were performed [18] and Nottingham prognostic index (NPI) was calculated [49, 50]. The modified NPI was calculated by the addition of 0.6 values for Her-2 positivity. Serum and tissue lysates were assayed for HER2 by a ready to use ELISA kit (Bioneovan Co, Ltd., China; assay range: 16-1000 Pg/ml) according to the manufacturer instructions and an amperometric magnetoimmunosensor according to Eletxigerra *et al.*, [11]. CA 15-3 was assayed by the electrochemiluminescence immunoassay (ECLIA) [Roche diagnostics GmbH, Germany; assay range = 1-300 U/ml; normal range for healthy non-pregnant females = 28.7-57.8U/ml (cut off value = 34.5 U/ml at 99% confidence interval)] using Cobas ® immunoassay analyser (Cobas 6000).

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS statistics for Windows, version 20 (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp. 2011). Qualitative data were described using number and percent. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to verify the normality of distribution. Quantitative data was described using range mean and standard deviation (SD). Significance of the obtained results was judged at the 5% level. F-test (analysis of variance: ANOVA) was used for normally distributed quantitative variables, to compare between more than two groups, and Post Hoc test (Tukey) for pairwise comparisons. Mann Whitney test was used for abnormally distributed quantitative variables, to compare between two studied groups. Kruskal Wallis test was used for abnormally distributed quantitative variables, to compare between more than two studied groups and Post Hoc (Dunn's multiple comparisons test) for pairwise comparisons. Spearman coefficient was used to correlate between two distributed abnormally quantitative variables. Receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) is generated by plotting sensitivity (TPR) on Y axis versus

1-specificity (FPR) on X axis at different cut off values. The area under the ROC curve denotes the diagnostic performance of the test. Area more than 50% gives acceptable performance and area about 100% is the best performance for the test. The ROC curve allows also a comparison of performance between two tests. Survival was analysed using Kaplan-Meier Survival curve.

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Authors contributions

Author	Role
NS, EZ	Conception & analysis of data
SA, AT, RN, EI	Interpretation of data & revision for important intellectual content
UE, MJ, CS, JM, MS	Conception, analysis of data, and revision for important intellectual content
EE	Conception, interpretation of data, preparation of the manuscript, revision for important intellectual content, and supervision

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Informed consents to participate in the study were taken

Blood (preoperative) and tissue (during elective surgery) samples were collected from subjects according to the ethical rules approved by the ethics committee of the medical research institute, Alexandria University, Egypt (IORG 0008812) (<https://mri.alexu.edu.eg/index.php/en/research-ethics/research-ethics-guidelines>). The study was performed in accordance with the ethical

standards of the Declaration of Helsinki (1964) and its subsequent amendments (https://mri.alexu.edu.eg/images/Declaration_of_Helsinki.pdf).

Consent for publication

Informed consents to publish the results were taken

Data availability: all data are available on personal request

Competing interests: None

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